

LAMB WAVE NON-DESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION OF REPAIRED COMPOSITE LAMINATED STRUCTURES

C. Soutis* and K. Diamanti

Aerospace Engineering, The University of Sheffield, S1 3JD, U.K

*Corresponding author: c.soutis@sheffield.ac.uk

SUMMARY

A cost and time effective inspection strategy for in-service health monitoring of composites is demonstrated using the A_0 Lamb wave mode at frequencies of 15-20 kHz. The method involves analysis of the transmitted and/or reflected wave generated by a piezoelectric device after interacting with defects. Here the applicability of the technique to inspect repaired composite laminates is explored.

Keywords: Layered Structures, non-destructive testing, Lamb waves, patch repairs, debonding.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are prime candidates for structural applications because of their high specific strength and stiffness but are expensive to maintain. The cost of inspection is approximately one third of the total cost of manufacturing and operating composite structures [1]. In order to realize their full potential it is essential that they are maintained in a safe and economical manner.

The evaluation of structural integrity using Lamb waves has long been acknowledged as a very promising technique [2,3]. Lamb waves are two-dimensional acoustic waves that can be generated in relatively thin solid plates with free boundaries and are also known as plate waves [4, 5]. They can be divided into symmetric S_n and anti-symmetric A_n modes according to their displacement pattern. Lamb waves excite the whole volume of the structure along the line between the transmitter and receiver and can propagate over considerably long distances. However, their dispersive nature and the existence of many modes simultaneously can complicate the interpretation of the acquired signal.

The use of Lamb waves for the inspection of multidirectional composite laminates is well documented but less work has been published for repaired composite structures. Repair techniques are regularly used in composites to restore structural integrity and prolong their life without reducing the components functionality. The use of Lamb waves for the quality assessment of adhesive joints though has received some attention [6-8]. Koh *et. al* [9] used surface bonded piezoelectric (PZTs) elements to excite the fundamental Lamb modes for the detection of debonding growth below a composite repair patch on an aluminium specimen. The sensors were able to detect the change in power transmission even when the damage was not located directly beneath them. A smart repair-patch with an integrated sensor network was designed by Ihn and Chang [10] to monitor crack growth in metallic structures under the composite patch. The

smart layer consisted of pairs of actuators and receivers, placed on either side of the crack propagation path and was inserted into the repair-patch at different ply locations.

In this paper a cost and time effective inspection strategy using the anti-symmetric or flexural Lamb mode A_0 , at low frequencies (15-20kHz) is applied to adhesively bonded repaired composite structures with composite patches. Since repairs are regularly used in composites to restore structural integrity it is important for a non-destructive technique (NDE) to be applicable to the structure after a repair has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Small piezoceramic wafer transducers have been selected for the generation and reception of low-frequency Lamb waves. Their low weight and volume makes them suitable for incorporation into smart structures. Operating as transmitters they transform electrical into mechanical energy. When an electrical field is applied in the direction normal to their surface, in-plane strains are mainly generated in the structure. Due to the coupling of the element to the structure, forces and moments are induced in the bonded area of the structure, generating elastic waves. As receivers they transform mechanical into electrical energy. When an elastic wave propagates through the structure the strains and stresses induced generate a voltage on the piezoceramic (PZT) element. These transducers have been successfully used to excite and capture the A_0 and S_0 modes at low frequencies in other studies [11-13].

Rectangular piezoceramic elements, 0.1 mm thick, supplied by Maplin Electronics U.K. Plc. were used as transmitters or receivers. They were mounted using instant glue at one edge of the composite specimens operating in pulse-echo mode. A Pentium II personal computer and an analog-to-digital PCI-MIO-16E-1 card together with LabVIEW software by National Instruments U.K. Ltd., Figure 1, were used to generate the signal, excite the transmitter and subsequently acquire and process the data from the receiver.

Figure 1. Schematic of the experimental set-up.

APPLICATIONS

Repaired Composite Beams

In the current work we are concerned only with the use of adhesively bonded external patches as a repair technique. This type of repair is widely employed since it is relatively easy to apply. It is mainly used in field repairs where rapid solutions are required and skilled personnel and adequate facilities are unavailable. The damage area

is usually removed by drilling a hole and a composite plate is either bolted or adhered to the surface of the component.

Figure 2. Geometry of repair specimens; dimensions in mm.

The single and double lap repair specimens used here are shown in Figure 2. Both the parent specimens and patch repairs were manufactured from T700UD/SE84LV UD carbon fibre-epoxy pre-preg tapes supplied by SP Systems to form $[\pm 45^{\circ}/0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_{2s}$ 2 mm thick quasi-isotropic laminates. A 9 mm hole was drilled to represent the removed damaged area, using a diamond coated tip drill piece. The required overlap length was calculated through analytical expressions [14]. Specimens without the hole were also prepared using the same patch length. No patch tapering was used. The specimens were 475 mm long and 30 mm wide. The centre of the patch in all the cases was at 250 mm. An SA80 SP Systems adhesive was used to bond the patches on the specimens.

Lamb wave inspection method

The specimens were instrumented with a pair of 5 mm by 15 mm piezoceramic elements. The specimens were wide enough to avoid reflections from the side edges but some were still evident. A small quantity of damping material (UHU[®] White Tack) was therefore used next to the transducers to isolate the reflection received from wave propagation along the length of the beams. A sampling frequency of 1.25 MS/s was used for the tests. Figure 3 shows the signals received from the double lap specimen

without a hole (r_{22}) at 15 kHz and 20 kHz with a sinusoidal excitation signal of 5.5 cycles enclosed in a Hanning window.

Figure 3. Response of the double lap repair specimen r_{22} at (a) 15 kHz and (b) 20 kHz excitation frequency.

At a frequency of 15 kHz it was observed that the reflections from the two ends of the patch overlapped to form the signal 3 on Figure 3 (a). However, at the higher frequency, Figure 3 (b), the smaller wavelength permitted a visible time separation between the two pulses seen as signals 3 and 4. Therefore the higher frequency was selected for the inspection of the repaired specimens. Similar results were observed for the rest of the specimens.

Figure 4. (a) Schematic of the single lap repair specimen r_{11} and (b) the correlation coefficient of the acquired Lamb wave response.

Figure 4 shows a schematic of the single lap repair specimen and the cross correlation coefficient of the monitored response, which is calculated as the product of the excitation pulse with the response of the structure at every time step. In general, when

there is a crack below the patch, Figure 4 (a), the propagation path of the wave in the parent specimen increases while the path in the repaired area of the specimen decreases. The wave propagates in the patched specimen at a higher velocity as the thickness at that point is double that of the parent specimen. Therefore in the cracked specimen the length of the parent specimen with the lower velocity increases and that causes the signal travelling through the whole propagation distance to be delayed. As the crack grows from point B to B' (crack length $l=BB'$) the peak of signal B will also be delayed. Finally the time that signal C appears depends on the length of both cracks and the relative difference between the velocities of the patched and parent specimen. If there is no debond at the beginning of the patch and the crack has only grown at the end (crack length $l=CC'$) the signal C will appear sooner on the time trace.

The resonant spectrum method [11] was used here to measure the phase velocity of the A_0 Lamb mode for the composite specimens, Figure 5.

Figure 5. Phase velocity in a quasi-isotropic composite laminate measured using the mechanical resonance method. Lamb theory estimates are also presented [11].

The group velocity and the time of flight (TOF) were also calculated at various frequencies. The time of flight of the input pulse, defined as the time it takes the input pulse to complete a round trip along the length of the specimen, is altered in the presence of damage. In general, the wave velocity changes in the damaged (cracked) area since the wave have to travel through a region of an effective thickness smaller than the undamaged configuration. In consequence, the fh product decreases and the phase velocity of the wave varies according to the dispersion curves of the material. The shape of the dispersion curve of the A_0 Lamb wave in the low fh product region is such that a reduction of the fh product produces a reduction of the phase and group velocities. Therefore, the TOF of an A_0 Lamb wave traveling in a specimen with debonding (interlaminar crack) is greater than that of a wave traveling in the same undamaged specimen. This difference, ΔTOF , can be estimated assuming that through the damage, the wave propagates via two sheets of material and that the thickest section is the fastest wave path, which is the one used for calculating the TOF . Therefore, the TOF of a wave propagating along an undamaged and damaged specimen are given, respectively, as

$$TOF_u = \frac{2L}{c_g} \quad \text{and} \quad TOF_d = \frac{2(L-l)}{c_g} + \frac{2l}{c_g} \quad (1)$$

from which the ΔTOF is obtained, i.e.,

$$\Delta TOF = 2l \left(\frac{1}{c_g} - \frac{1}{c'_g} \right) \quad (2)$$

where L is the length of the specimen, l is crack (debonding) size, and c_g and c'_g are the group velocities in the undamaged and damaged regions, respectively.

Numerical and experimental results

A Finite Element model was built in Abaqus 6.3 [15] to check the TOF behaviour described above. In the analysis 4-noded general shell elements were used for the parent specimen. The patch was also modelled with shell elements on top of the parent specimen using multipoint constraints at the common nodes. A single lap repair specimen was built having the same dimensions as the test specimen r₁₁. Nodes were disconnected gradually to obtain the response of the cracked (debonded) structure. Cracks were introduced at the first edge of the patch and the TOF changes between the signals A and B are plotted against the crack length in Figure 6 (a). Deviation from the linear behaviour is expected due to the difficulty of identifying the peak of the signals at low frequency. However, a clear indication of the debond growth below the patch is shown from the delay in the signal. In Figure 6 (b) the crack was gradually increased from side 2 and the TOF between signals C and D is plotted against the crack length.

Figure 6. FE analysis: TOF increase with increasing crack length (a) front of patch (BB') and (b) end of patch (CC').

In order to introduce a crack beneath the patch, 4-point bending experiments were undertaken. The testing fixture consisted of two parts, each having two movable cylindrical surfaced noses. The specimens were fixed at two points 150 mm apart for the specimens with the shorter patch and 200 mm apart for the longer one, the patch was located centrally at the support span. The two loading points were spaced 25 mm away from their adjacent support point for all the specimens. The support span was 100 mm and 150 mm for the shorter and longer patch respectively. The load was applied at a rate of 1 mm/min until a crack appeared at the skin-patch interface which was under tension.

For the 2.5 mm thick specimens cracks appeared. However for the 1.25 mm specimens the deflections were large and the experiments had to be stopped before a crack was

introduced due to space restriction of the fixtures. For these specimens a smaller crack was initially introduced by a sharp blade and then its length was increased manually by applying bending load. By these means it was possible to start the cracks separately at the ends of the patch and therefore monitor the differences in the mechanical response of specimens. In order to assist the reading of the crack length the sides of the specimens were painted white and markings were printed at 1 mm intervals.

Figure 7. Response of the pristine (a) and damaged (b) single lap repair specimen r_{11} ; crack BB' is 10 mm and crack CC' is 18 mm.

The cross correlation between the excitation pulse and response of the structure was computed to identify the time difference between the individual wave packets.

Figure 7 (a) shows the response of the un-cracked repaired specimen r_{11} . The group velocities were experimentally measured at the parent specimen of the same lay-up and material at various frequencies and are reported in Table 1. Using these values and the TOF measurements, the length of the different areas in the repaired specimen can be calculated. The results are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Experimental values of group velocity for the quasi-isotropic laminate T700/SE84LV.

fh (kHzmm)	Cg (m/s)
25	898
50	1159
75	1288
100	1355

Good correlation is achieved for the AB and CD distances but agreement was poor for the BC distance. This is because the velocity used for the wave propagation in that region was taken from the parent material without any adhesive. The presence of the adhesive will decrease the stiffness and therefore the velocity in that region giving a more representative value.

After the 4-point bending experiment the cracks BB' and CC' were measured with a magnifying camera to be 10 mm and 18 mm in length, respectively. The response of the damaged specimen r_{11} is depicted in

Figure 7 (b). It can be observed that a very strong signal was reflected from the crack BB' which travelled back and forth within the AB distance causing multiple reflections. The estimated crack length was 12 mm instead of 10 mm as presented in Table 2. Little energy was transmitted to the rest of the specimen and the signals from points C and D were not recorded, therefore no information is given for the other end of the patch.

Table 2. Predicted debond in repair specimen r_{11} (true crack length BB' 10mm).

Distance	TOF (ms)	Estimated value (mm)	True value (mm)	Error (%)
AB	0.326	189	191	1
BC	0.198	134	118	14
CD	0.296	172	166	4
AB'	0.350	203	201	1

The difference in the TOF of the individual signals for the r_{21} , r_{22} specimens and the predicted crack length are given in Table 3. The time difference between the signals from the edge of the beam A or D and the patch B or C correspond to the lengths AB and CD, respectively as illustrated in Figure 4 (a). When a crack is present the TOF increases; this is attributed to the wave propagation along the cracked part of the specimen BB' or CC'. In this specimen cracks appeared only at the side of the patched specimen that was in tension. Therefore the velocity for the 3.75 mm thick part of the specimen at $fh = 75$ kHz mm frequency-thickness product was used to calculate the crack length. Good estimation of the crack growth is achieved which is consistent for both r_{21} , r_{22} specimens. The predicted crack length from the Lamb wave response is also presented for the thin r_{31} , r_{32} single lap repair specimens shown in Table 4, where the crack was separately increased in length from point B and C of the patch.

Table 3. Predicted debond in the double lap repair specimens, r_{21} and r_{22}

Distance	TOF (ms)	Distance	TOF (ms)	Difference TOF (μ s)	Measured crack (mm)	True crack (mm)
r_{21}						
AB	0.347	AB'	0.353	6	3.9	5
CD	0.313	C'D	0.318	5	3.2	3
r_{22}						
AB	0.347	AB'	0.355	8	5.2	6
CD	0.317	C'D	0.323	6	3.9	3

Table 4. Predicted debond in the single lap repair specimens, r_{31} and r_{32} .

Distance	TOF (ms)	Distance	TOF (ms)	Difference TOF (μ s)	Measured crack (mm)	True crack (mm)
r_{31}						
AB	0.473	AB'	0.481	8	3.6	4
AB	0.473	AB'	0.501	28	12.6	11
AB	0.473	AB'	0.507	34	15.3	15

		I_{32}				
CD	0.438	C'D	0.462	24	10.8	7
CD	0.438	C'D	0.478	40	18.0	15
CD	0.438	C'D	0.489	51	22.9	20

Finally, damage was introduced outside of the repaired region in the FE model. Damage was modelled as a 30 mm long area of reduced material stiffness properties extending across the width of the specimen. It was located after the patch at 400 mm from the transducers. It can be observed, Figure 8, that the signals coming from the patch boundaries appear at the same position in time as the undamaged specimen, however the reflection from the edge of the specimen is delayed, indicating damage between the points C and D of the specimen.

Figure 8. FE response of a repair specimen with damage outside the patch.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

It is shown that the low-frequency (10-50 kHz) A_0 Lamb waves can be successfully used to interrogate composite structures after a repair has been undertaken. Changes in the response of the propagated pulses have been used to detect and locate debonding between the patch and substrate. The technique is very sensitive to small changes of the structural integrity of the repaired structure. Hairline cracks below the patch as small as 3 mm in length were successfully detected. Tapering of the patch should be investigated as it will affect the wave reflection from the patch edges. However, when cracks have initiated it is thought that the behaviour is going to be similar to that described in the present paper. The method has been applied successfully to detect damage in larger composite structures [16-18].

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